

CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC PARAMETERS OF RHEUMATIC HEART DISEASE AND FEATURES OF THE COURSE.

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Abstract: In the next 15-20 years, the clinical picture of RF (rheumatic fever) has changed significantly. Most authors note an extremely low incidence of severe rheumatic carditis, a decrease in mortality and relapses of the disease, a transition to a monocindromic form of the disease, low-symptomatic and latent variants of the course, etc. American researchers note that due to the low prevalence of the disease, most doctors still do not know about complex and changing clinical picture of the disease.

Keywords: Rheumatic fever, chorea, carditis, acute heart failure, cardiac rheumatic fever, chronic heart failure

INTRODUCTION: One of the leading clinical syndromes of RF is acute or subacute polyarthritis, characterized by complete regression of inflammatory changes in all affected joints within 2-3 weeks, and under the influence of modern anti-inflammatory therapy, this period can be reduced to several hours or days. The

frequency of polyarthritis ranges from 60 to 100% according to different authors. The most commonly injured are the ankle and knee (90%), forearm and elbow (61%), less often the shoulder (44%), hip (31%), hip, acromial (6%) joints. Atypical manifestations of the articular syndrome are less common: monoarthritis, small joints of the palms of the hands and feet, the cervical spine a relapse of arthritis occurs during treatment. As for primary rheumatic heart disease, opinions differ here. According to most authors, the incidence of primary rheumatic heart disease is very high and ranges from 88.5 to 100%. Meanwhile, according to other authors, at the first attack of rheumatism it is not so high - 50-69% and even very low - 3-38%.

Such a discrepancy is difficult to explain only by the polymorphism of clinical symptoms and course variants in different regions and countries of the world. It is known that with pronounced polyarthritis, the clinical signs of rheumatic heart disease may be little known. Therefore, an unusual interpretation of both the symptoms of carditis and the disease as a whole is not excluded. However, the American Heart Association's information on the correct application of the restored Jones criteria (1944) accurately describes the damage to the heart in primary rheumatic heart disease. It was noted above that at the first attack of rheumatic heart disease, overdiagnosis of RF or a hypodiagnostic state is possible. On the other hand, the WHO research team believes that patients (especially in developing countries) first visit a doctor without reliable anamnestic, clinical and laboratory data that meet the Jones criteria, which have been revised for acuterheumatic heart disease. For greater adequacy of the criteria, it is necessary that in clinical experience it was established that in these cases the diagnosis of RF in such patients can be considered justified only if cardiomyopathy and myopericarditis of other etiologies are excluded, as well as circulatory failure as a result of stagnation in valvular heart disease. Therefore, it should be noted the importance of revolutionary research methods for the early diagnosis of rheumatic heart disease (phonocardiography, echocardiography, Doppler echocardiography). Rheumatic lesion of the nervous system – chorea minor - occurs mainly in children,

less often in adolescents, in 6-31% of cases. However, the Brazilian authors showed that the incidence of chorea was quite high and amounted to 44.8%. Rheumatic chorea can only be diagnosed with the exclusion of other diseases of the nervous system, when other criteria for the disease (RF) are not met. Some authors believe that erythema annulare and rheumatoid arthritis have

reduced their diagnostic value to a minimum due to declining detection in the last 2-3 decades.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: In foreign countries, for the diagnosis of RF, the criteria proposed by WHO (1989) are used. The fact that rheumatic heart disease remains difficult to diagnose even in modern conditions is associated with the following conditions:

- streptococcal genesis of the transferred nasopharyngeal infection is not always clear;
- the titer of antistreptococcal antibodies may be low;
- Throat shots often fail;
- the initial manifestation of carditis is less pronounced;
- signs of systemic inflammation will not be sufficiently pronounced.

In the 21st century, there is an urgent need to revise the classification and presentation of the disease inThe term acute rheumatic fever (ARF) (rather than rheumatism) is more appropriate because it draws the physician's attention to the diagnosis of group A betahemolytic streptococcus (AGBS) infection, thus emphasizing the need for acute antibiotic use. Period for eradication (primary prevention) and prevention of recurrent attacks (secondary prevention). As for the term “primary rheumatic carditis (rheumatism)”, clinical experience has expanded this concept to include any initially diagnosed heart defects, both with mitral valve prolapse, a manifestation of hypermobility syndrome, and with large and medium ones, used to

refer to arthralgia caused by instability in the joints. In addition, the last 20 years of dynamic echocardiography studies have shown that valvulitis is considered the main component of rheumatic heart disease and can occur together with myopericarditis, manifesting as organic heart murmurs. The defeat of the heart in the form of myopericarditis without valvulitis, as observed, is generally not characteristic of measles, but is diagnosed in comparison with carditis of a different etiology (mainly viral). On the other hand, the clinical symptoms of carditis may be mild in migratory polyarthritis, which is clearly expressed in acute rheumatic fever, or in chorea minor. Therefore, the diagnostic significance of the use of Doppler echocardiography increases, since it is possible to see the anatomical structure of the heart and the state of intracardiac blood flow, including mitral and aortic insufficiency, the first sign of valvulitis. In particular, an outbreak of acute rheumatic fever in the United States showed valvular heart disease in 47% of patients with rheumatoid arthritis and in 57% "isolated" chorea on echocardiography. In view of the above, modified Kisel-Jones diagnostic criteria for acute rheumatic fever were included in the ExoKG surveys (Table 4). In connection with the predominant form of joint damage - migratory oligoarthritis and less often - monoarthritis of large joints, it is necessary to distinguish them from arthritis of other genesis, including post-streptococcal arthritis. Poststreptococcal arthritis has a distinct clinical and epidemiological characteristic: a short latent period after ABGS of tonsillitis/pharyngitis; persistent, usually symmetrical damage to large joints; absence of carditis and chorea, slow response to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory therapy; after treatment, complete regression of the disease without radiological changes in 2-4 months from the onset of the disease. The problem of differential diagnosis of "isolated" (that is, in the absence of other diagnostic criteria) rheumatic chorea in subsequent years was exacerbated by the recently interpreted PANDAS syndrome (childhood autoimmune neuropsychiatric disorders associated with group A streptococcal infection), pediatricians and pediatric

psychoneurologists. This syndrome is characterized by: obsessive-compulsive disorders (obsessive thoughts + obsessive situations (unpleasant));

1) the onset of the disease in the prepubertal period (up to 12 years);

2) acute onset and undulating course;

3) chronological affiliation to ABGS, confirmed by a recent microbiological study (isolation of the pathogen in a throat swab and / or an increase in serological also and anti-DNA-ase titer);

4) neurological disorders (choreic hyperkinesia) accordance with internationally accepted terminology

RESULTS: In the diagnosis and differential diagnosis of acute rheumatic fever, it is often difficult to interpret evidence that ABGS infection of the throat is the cause of the disease. The main cases of a more correct interpretation of the results obtained include:

A positive ABGS culture taken from the throat of patients can be both evidence of an active infection and confirmation of asymptomatic carriage of this microbe.

1. A negative microbiological test and a negative rapid antigen test do not rule out active ABGS infection.

2. The diagnostic value of testing immunity to streptococci increases with the simultaneous detection of 2 types of antibodies (antistreptolysin-o, antideoxyribonuclease-V), but we should not forget that the above antibodies can also be observed after an infection caused by β -hemolytic streptococcus.

3. With late carditis or "isolated" chorea, the titer of antistreptococcal antibodies may be normal. In patients with a rheumatic history, a second attack is treated as a new episode of urticaria, and not a recurrence of the first. In this situation (especially when the diagnosis of carditis against the background of established rheumatic heart disease is very difficult), the diagnosis of acute rheumatic fever is made only when one "major" or only "small" criterion is combined with an increased or increasing titer of antistreptococcal antibodies. The final diagnosis can be made only with the exclusion

of intercurrent diseases associated with heart defects and their complications (primarily infective endocarditis).

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is determined based on the classifications of V.Kh. Vasilenko and N.D. Strajesko and NYHA. According to modern neurohumoral theory, the main cause of the development of CHF syndrome is hyperactivation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS) and sympathoadrenal systems. That is, if the main cause of CHF is the action of an excess of neurohormones, then the blockade of their effects with AAFI should theoretically lead to a 100% positive clinical outcome. In real life, AAFI can reduce the risk of death in CHF patients by only 23% on average. In recent years, many clinical facts have appeared that it is difficult to explain CHF only by an increase in the activity of neurohormones. Along with neurohormones, some other (including immune) mechanisms play a central role in the pathogenesis of the disease. The participation of the immune system in the pathogenesis of CHF may seem incomprehensible only at first glance: it is well known that the body's immune defense "works" not only with the aggression of an infection, but also in response to any stressful effect, including ischemia, hemodynamic overload, shows a reaction during intoxication and etc. Cytokines play an important role in the new model of CHF. Cytokines are low molecular weight protein mediators that provide intercellular communication. Depending on their functions, they are divided into pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines. The first group consists of interleukin (yl) IL-1, IL-2, IL-6, IL-8, IL-12, tumor necrosis factor- α (it- α), interferons. The second group includes IL-4, IL-10, IL-11, IL-7. Cytokines control the amplitude and duration of the inflammatory and immune response, so they are produced and secreted transiently and have a short half-life. They have a very low concentration (picogram) effect when they bind to high affinity receptors on the surface of target cells. In most cases, cytokines secreted by cells have a local (autocrine, i.e., on their producer cells and paracrine, i.e., on other target cells) endocrine effect to a very small extent. The action of various cytokines on each other and on the cell can be synergistic, antagonistic or additive

(complementary). In CHF, there is an imbalance between pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines. Pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1, IL-3, IL-6, IL-8, α -TNF), cellular receptors for cytokines and their soluble forms (sTNF- α -P55, sTNF- α -P75, sL-2P and etc.), adhesion molecules (superfamily of immunoglobulins, integrins and selectins), chemoattractants, apoptosis receptors, growth mediators, neopterin. The immune system produces the synthesis of anti-inflammatory cytokines -lymphocytes, monocytes, macrophages, as well as endotheliocytes, smooth muscle cells.

CONCLUSION: Thus, the "cytokine" model of the pathogenesis of CHF does not challenge the neurohumoral theory, but expands our understanding of the development of CHF. The involvement of inflammatory mediators in the disease scheme expands the "base of the therapeutic approach" and expands the prospects for improving the effectiveness of the treatment of patients with CHF.

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Urakovich, TS Mizamovich, TM Matmusaevich *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3 (3), 45-48, 2022

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Достижения науки и образования, 72-75, 2022

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ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ Учредители: Олимп, 72-75, 0